

Rise of Rebel

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Abstract— The “Rise of Rebel” is an open-world RPG (role-playing game) game. Players will be able to play our protagonist “RON” similar to all RPG games, this game is also set in a virtual world full of mysteries. Rise of Rebel is an action-adventure game played from a third-person perspective. The main objective of the game is to tell the stories of our protagonist as well as provide players an experience of all his adventures. As the game is story-driven the objectives and mission in the game will be based on the problems and difficulties faced by our protagonist on his adventure, the player will have to solve the problems to see and experience how the journey unfolds. Games are now considered a useful tool for learning and educational practices. This research will facilitate the developers in understanding the game mechanics of an RPG open-world game. The player may run, jump and fight, etc.

Keywords— Unity, NavMeshAgent, Action-Adventure Game, Open-World Game

I. INTRODUCTION

In this game, we have tried to make an open-world RPG game where we are trying to convey a story of a boy belonging to a family of farmers living in a small village where his family would grow crops and sell them to earn a living for their family but one night when the boy had gone to another village for selling his crops a tragic incident occurs when he came back, he saw the entire village was burned to ashes, worried for his family the boy ran to investigate. Now, what was the reason behind the tragedy where his family was alive all the answers will be given in the game? The game involves Open world game-play, Treasure exploration, as well as a Fighting mechanics to give players a good experience The game focuses on the time when "Monarchy" was a thing, so the game focuses on hand and lots of sword fights, Giving the players an experience of what it's likes to be sword-man in that period of time. Rise of Rebel is an action-adventure game played from a third-person

perspective.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are a lot of popular games out there, one of those games was the “Prince of Persia” series. This series become very popular at the time and was considered a masterpiece with an interesting story. But that does not mean it didn't have any flaws. After playing all the installations from the series, we have found some flaws as well as some ideas on how to enhance the experience of such games. Which inspired us to make our own game with all the ideas on how to enhance the overall experience and a story of our own.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

“Rise of Rebel” is an open-world RPG game based on “The unity” game engine. All the assets used in the game are either self-made or gathered from the unity asset store. The coding language used in the game is “C#” as Unity uses C# for Scripting. The assets are made using “blender” which is a free tool used for 3D modeling etc. The coding environment used for coding is “Visual studios”. The main objective of the game is to enhance the gameplay experience of the players by adding some new features which were not available in the existing system and providing players with a fun experience. The only purpose of this game is Entertainment.

Figure 1: Block diagram of Proposed System

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IV. RESULTS

Figure 2: Home Page

Figure 3: Volume Setting

Figure 4: Starting Page of Game

Figure a

Figure b

Figure c

Figure a, b, and c shows different implemented screens with one player performing a given task.

After playing their first game with this expansion, players can choose whether they wish to use the Rise of the Rebel set of mission cards or the set of mission cards from the base game.

V. ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

- A true open-world RPG experience.
- An equipment inventory management system has been added.
- A new combat system has been added for better gameplay.
- A realistic and detailed environment has been added.
- Modes of transport have been added.
- Improve your mystery-solving skill.
- Explore great village life experiences.
- A new feature was added to this game.

VI. APPLICATION

- The one and only purpose of making this game is Entertainment.
- Explore the vast open world.

CONCLUSION

The End conclusion of this game is entertainment only. The only purpose of making this game is because we want our players to have a fun time playing it. Also, we want to inspire more and more people to become part of the fast-growing game development industry.

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